

SIMPLIFIED DETERMINATION METHOD OF LONG-TERM VISCOELASTIC BEHAVIOR OF AMORPHOUS RESIN

H. Cai^{1*}, M. Nakada², Y. Miyano²

¹ School of Materials Science and Engineering, Xi'an Jiaotong University, Xi'an, China

² Materials System Research Laboratory, Kanazawa Institute of Technology, Hakusan, Japan

* Corresponding author(hntsai@mail.xjtu.edu.cn)

Keywords: *Polymer resin, Viscoelastic, Time-temperature superposition principle, Accelerated testing methodology*

1 Abstract

The time-temperature superposition principle was applied by authors to predict accurately the long-term viscoelastic behavior of amorphous resin at a temperature below the glass transition temperature from measuring the short-term viscoelastic behavior at elevated temperatures. In this paper, the simplified determination method of long-term viscoelastic behavior of amorphous resin using dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) tests is proposed. The auto-shifting method is used to get the smooth storage modulus master curve and the time-temperature shift factors. The validity of the simplified determination method is analyzed.

2 Introduction

The mechanical behavior of polymer resin shows time and temperature dependence, called viscoelastic behavior not only above the glass transition temperature T_g but also below T_g . Therefore, the mechanical behavior of FRP also shows time and temperature dependence even below T_g which is within the normal operating temperature ranges. The time and temperature dependent mechanical behavior of FRP has been studied by Aboudi et al. [1], Gates [2], Miyano et al. [3] and Sullivan [4].

In our previous paper [5], the time-temperature superposition principle (TTSP) was applied to predict accurately the long-term viscoelastic behavior of amorphous resin at a temperature below T_g from measuring the short-term viscoelastic behavior at elevated temperatures.

In this paper, the simplified determination method of long-term viscoelastic behavior of amorphous resin using DMA tests is proposed to determine the long term viscoelastic behavior of amorphous resin at a temperature below T_g . The short-term viscoelastic

behavior is measured using DMA tests under various frequencies and temperatures. The auto-shifting method is used to get the smooth storage modulus master curve and the time-temperature shift factors. The validity of the simplified determination method is analyzed.

3 Theories

3.1 Formulation of master curves of creep compliance

The viscoelastic behaviors of the matrix resin can be represented by the storage modulus E' which can easily be measured with DMA conducted at various frequencies and temperatures. Note that D_c can approximately be obtained from E' by using the approximate formula:

$$D_c(t) \sim 1/E(t), \quad (1)$$

$$E(t) \cong E'(\omega) |_{\omega \rightarrow 2/\pi}. \quad (2)$$

The master curve of D_c can be represented by two tangential lines, whose slopes are m_g and m_r , respectively, as Fig.1(a) shows. The reduced time at an intersection of the tangential lines are called as the reduced glassy time t'_g at a reference temperature T_o . With these parameters, the master curve of D_c can be fitted with the following formula:

$$\log D_c = \log D_{c,o}(t'_o, T_o) + \log \left[\left(\frac{t'}{t'_o} \right)^{m_g} + \left(\frac{t'}{t'_g} \right)^{m_r} \right] \quad (3)$$

Where $D_{c,o}$ is an initial creep compliance at the initial reduced time t'_o at a reference temperature T_o . The time-temperature shift factor $a_{T_o}(T)$ that is the amount of the horizontal shift, can be fitted with the following equation:

$$\log a_{T_0}(T) = \frac{\Delta H_1}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) H(T_g - T) + \left[\frac{\Delta H_1}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T_g} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) + \frac{\Delta H_2}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_g} \right) \right] (1 - H(T_g - T)) \quad (4)$$

Where G is gas constant, ΔH is activation energy, T_g is glass transition temperature.

The temperature shift factor, $b_{T_0}(T)$, which is the amount of the vertical shift, can be fitted with the following equation:

$$\log b_{T_0}(T) = [b_1(T_g - T_0) + b_0] H(T_g - T) + \left[b_1(T_g - T_0) + b_0 + \log \frac{T_g}{T} \right] (1 - H(T_g - T)) \quad (5)$$

Where b_i is coefficient.

Figure 1 Concept of formulation of master curve of creep compliance, time-temperature and temperature shift factors

3.2 Automatic shifting algorithm

Smooth master curves were obtained by both horizontal and vertical translation of individual storage modulus curves. In order to minimize the error by manual shift, an automatic shift procedure with high order polynomial was used to fit the master curve. Figure 2 show the sum of the square of the error for two segments can be minimized from the

optimum solution with second order polynomial. Optimum shift method using fourth order polynomial was used. For every combination of shift factors, the shift factors resulting in the minimum sum of the square of the errors is the final optimal solution.

Figure 2 Automatic shift for construction of master curve

4 Preparation of specimen

The material used in this study is a general purpose epoxy resin jER 828. The hardener and cure accelerator used are MHAC-P and 2-ethyl-4-methylimidazole, respectively. The epoxy resin plates were molded by casting and cured at 70°C for 12 hours. The DMA test specimens cut from epoxy resin plates were post-cured at 150°C for 4 hours and at 190°C for 2 hours. Then the cured specimens were cooled at a rate of 0.5°C per minute. In order to minimize the physical aging effect during the DMA tests, the heat treatment for the cured specimens was conducted at 100°C for 167 hours in a constant temperature chamber before creep test.

The strain amplitude of 0.06% by the sinusoidal wave with frequency range of 0.01-10Hz was applied to specimen, as shown in Fig.3. The width, thickness and length of specimen are 6.4mm, 1.6mm and 50 mm, respectively. The span is 38.6 mm. The temperatures ranged from 25 °C to 140°C.

Figure 3 Test specimen configuration

5 Results and discussion

5.1 Master curve of storage modulus by DMA tests

The left side of Fig.4 shows the storage modulus E' versus testing time t ($=1/f$) at various temperatures T of epoxy resin. The master curve of E' versus the reduced time t' was constructed by shifting E' at various constant temperatures along the log scale of t as shown in the right side of Fig.4. Since E' at various temperatures can be superimposed smoothly, the TTSP is applicable for E' .

Figure 4 Master curve of storage modulus by DMA tests

Figure 5 shows time-temperature shift factor a_{T_0} and temperature shift factor b_{T_0} obtained by constructing the master curves of the storage modulus shown in the right sides of Fig.4. From these results the time-temperature shift factor can be obtained accurately and easily by using DMA tests and automatic shift method.

Figure 5 Time-temperature shift factor and temperature shift factor for the storage modulus

5.2 Comparison of master curves of creep compliance

As comparison, creep tests were performed to compare the creep compliances and time-temperature shift factors. The test specimens are same as described in [5].

Master curves of creep compliance by creep tests are shown in the Fig.6. The left side of Fig.6 shows the D_c versus time t at various temperatures T of epoxy resin measured by creep tests. The smooth master curve of D_c can be constructed by shifting D_c at various constant temperatures vertically as well as horizontally using automatic shift method, as shown in the right sides.

The master curves of compliance obtained from the DMA test and creep tests are shown in Fig.7, where the creep compliance from DMA is obtained using the inverse of E' . The fitted master curves shown in Fig.7 are obtained using the formulae (3). The master curves from DMA and creep test agrees well with each other.

The formulated parameters for creep compliance are listed in Table. 1.

Figure 6 Master curve of creep compliance by creep tests

Figure 7 Comparison of master curves of creep compliances from creep and DMA tests

Figure 9 Comparison of temperature shift factors

5.3 Comparison of shift factors

Figure 8 show the comparison of the time-temperature shift factor a_{T_0} those obtained from the construction of master curves of E' and D_c , respectively. The a_{T_0} obtained from DMA and creep test agree well with each other below glass transition temperature T_g . Above T_g , the a_{T_0} obtained from creep tests drops rapidly. The DMA tests are applicable to the temperature above T_g . However, the creep tests are not applicable to the temperature above T_g .

Figure 9 show the comparison of the temperature shift factor b_{T_0} those obtained from the construction of master curves of E' and D_c , respectively. The b_{T_0} obtained from DMA and creep test agree well with each other below T_g .

The formulated parameters for time-temperature shift factor and temperature shift factor are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 List of formulation parameters

	DMA	CREEP
D_{C0} [1/GPa]	3.70	0.27
t_0 [min]	1	1
m_g	0.004	0.011
m_r	0.358	0.492
t'_g at T_0 [min]	4.5×10^7	7.5×10^7
ΔH_1 [KJ/mol]	134.0	117.0
ΔH_2 [KJ/mol]	670.0	1245.0
T_g [°C]	125	125
b_0	0.002	0.001
b_1	0.010	0.013

Figure 8 Comparison of time-temperature shift factors

6 Conclusions

The dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) tests were conducted under various frequencies and temperatures. The creep tests for epoxy resin were conducted also for various temperatures. The same master curves of compliance and time-temperature shift factor can be obtained from DMA tests and creep test based on the time-temperature superposition principle (TTSP). The automatic shift method was proposed and used to construct master curves for storage modulus and creep compliance. The simplified determination method of long-term viscoelastic behavior for amorphous resin using DMA tests based on the TTSP was verified.

Acknowledgement: This work is supported by National Science Foundation of China (No. 61079011), and supported by the Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities.

References

- [1] Aboudi, J. and Cederbaum, G., Analysis of Viscoelastic Laminated Composite Plates, *Composite Structures*, 12, pp.243-256 (1989).
- [2] Gates, T., Experimental Characterization Nonlinear Rate Dependent Behavior in Advanced Polymer Matrix Composites, *Experimental Mechanics*, 32, pp.68-73 (1992).
- [3] Miyano, Y., Kanemitsu, M., Kunio, T. and Kunh, H., Role of Matrix Resin on Fracture Strengths of Unidirectional CFRP, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 20, pp.520-538 (1986).
- [4] Miyano, Y., Amagi, S. and Kanemitsu, M., Flexural Fracture Behavior of Carbon/Aramid Hybrid Unidirectional Reinforced FRP Laminates, *Proceeding of International Symposium on FRP/CM*, pp.1250-1260 (1988).
- [5] Nakada, M., Miyano, Y., Cai, H. and Kasamori, M., Modified Time-Temperature Superposition Principle for Viscoelastic Behavior of Amorphous Resin (To be published in *Mechanics of Time-Dependent Materials*).